

SPORTS PUBLICATIONS: LANGUAGE, STYLE AND EDITORIAL ISSUES

Nargiza Mirzaeva

PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of

Uzbek Language and Literature

of Journalism and

Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan

Abstract. The use of language in a newspaper depends on the audience of the material. This is especially important in specialized publications. This article describes the language and style of materials related to sports. In addition, an analysis of methodological errors found in sports texts is given.

Keywords: specialized publication, sports journalism, sports websites, language, style, editing, grammatical errors.

It is known that the rapid recognition of each country on a global scale and increased prestige depend on a number of factors, including sports. Today, sports have become so popular that it is not an exaggeration to say that millions of people regularly play sports.

Sport serves to create morally mature, spiritually rich, highly educated, physically strong, mature in all respects. In addition, along with sports, press publications specializing in sports programs, television and radio programs are developing all over the world as a branch of general journalism. Look at any publication and you will see that sports have not been left behind. Because this area is becoming an important factor in expanding the audience of this publication. In addition, newspapers and magazines dedicated only to sports are published in all countries of the world. There are similar publications in our republic. So, it is clear that along with sports, its journalism is gaining high positions among the masses.

We can learn about the extent to which sports journalism, which has become more professional, is developing in Uzbekistan from the activities of publications specializing in this field.

The resolution of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated February 15 of this year “On measures to further improve the management system in the field of culture and sports” opened a new era in the development of sports in our country. According to

the resolution, the State Committee for Physical Education and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created. Involving a significant part of the population in sports, raising a physically healthy generation, developing the sports industry and infrastructure, holding mass sports events and competitions in cities and regions, selecting, training and improving the skills of talented athletes together with the National Olympic Committee. Its main objectives were identified as sports federations and associations, personnel training, the introduction of modern technologies in the field and the expansion of international relations.

It is natural that websites specializing in sports such as "Sport", "Interfutbol", TV channel "Sport", "championat.asia", "stadion.uz", "tribuna.uz" differ from each other in terms of language and style. Journalists working in it should know the terms of their specialized sport well. So to speak, he should know his work from thread to needle. After all, in the process of conveying information, it is necessary to explain to the audience the words that require some explanation.

Information needs to be communicated to the public in understandable and simple language. The reader expects a lively, fast and easy-to-understand style from the newspaper materials, not a standard, regular, strict way of expression. Accordingly, avoiding speech patterns and patterns encourages journalists to search for new tools, new ways of expression, thereby ensuring the effectiveness of information and creating their own personal style, conducting research on its further improvement. First of all, based on world experience, let's look at our newspapers from the perspective of international sports publications. Almost 90% of foreign sports publications are printed in "A-2" format. The main goal is to increase the impact of photos and captions. Photos are the heart of sports newspapers. A great deal of information can be conveyed through a single photo and caption. Some of our newspapers have taken this into account and are using these methods effectively. The various, eye-pleasing pictures on the first pages of the newspaper will be the proof of our above opinion.

Sports journalism should also be more popular in reporting events in the world of sports. There is a disconnect between sports journalism and the audience these days. What is it? Of course, a more literary approach to the language of journalism, avoiding the vernacular, is one of those reasons. If we use vernacular words instead of violent literary language, we lose that disconnect, especially in spoken language. Especially a sports commentator should embody this quality. One of the sports is football. It is a game of millionaires. Needless to say about it. Every fan knows some

of his terms. The words ball, goal, penalty are used a lot. But at the same time, football terms such as pressing and raid have entered the speech, so finding an Uzbek alternative to these words requires a journalist to know the language well. Therefore, the journalist should comment on the terms used in the process of using these words.

In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the language, style and, of course, the title of the text given in each publication material. A journalist is required to work tirelessly and work on himself in order to deliver the material effectively and clearly to the audience. The most important factor in the expression of opinions is the thorough knowledge of the possibilities of language tools and the ability to use them in practice. For example, while looking at the materials on the pages of "Interfutbol" newspaper, we notice spelling and stylistic errors in the texts.

"Our compatriots, who celebrated the championship of Kazakhstan with "Ordabasi" yesterday, answered *this success and several other interesting questions (ушбу маваффақият ва бошқа бир нечта қизиқарли саволларга жавоб беришди)* in an interview with the reporter of Championat.asia.uz" [1,12]. The sentence is logically understandable, but stylistically incorrect. A spelling mistake was also made in the sentence.

"*in some ways, Diego was lucky (қайсидир жиҳатдан Диегога омад қулиб боқди):* yes, "Seville" is buried in problems, but he has no obligation to achieve high results, free from excessive pressures" [1, 21].

"Koreans buy several *T-shirts with the names* (тушурилган футболкалардан) of their compatriots from this store every day" [1, 28]. There is a spelling mistake in the sentence. The word "Тушурилган" is misspelled. Used in a colloquial manner.

Another example. "*Lionel Messi and Cristiano Ronaldo, who have risen to the level of genius in modern football, are at opposite poles in terms of character, behavior and attitude to everyday life. Their views may even conflict in some respects*" (Замонавий футболда даҳо даражасига кўтарилган Лионель Месси ва Криштиану Роналду феъл-атвор, хулқ ва кундалик ҳаётга муносабат нуқтаи назаридан турли қутбларда. Уларнинг қарашлари ҳаттоки, қарама-қарши келиши ҳам мумкин баъзи жиҳатларда) [2,27]. The sentence is grammatically incorrect.

So, when publishing news and analytical materials about sports in the press, when commenting on sports-related materials in radio and television broadcasts, oral and written forms of speech are used, it is logical that both speeches should be literate

and popular if the statement is used together with a photograph or image, it must be harmonious. To achieve this, specialized sports journalists in the press, radio and television are required to constantly work and research their performances.

REFERENCES:

1. Миллий жамоага боримни беришга тайёрман. //Интерфутбол, 26 октябрь 2023 йил, 85-сон.
2. Бир йилда уч уриниш. //Интерфутбол, 26 октябрь 2023 йил, 85-сон.
3. Ашаддий рақиблар, ибратли уйғунлик. // Интерфутбол, 26 октябрь 2023 йил, 84-сон.
4. Nargiza Mirzayeva. (2023). RERAYTER FAOLIYATIDA MATN BILAN ISHLASHNING O‘ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI. *Konferensiyalar | Conferences*, 1(1), 53–58. Retrieved from <https://uzresearchers.com/index.php/Conferences/article/view/1136>
5. Mirzayeva, N. (2014). JOURNALIST SPECIALIZATION IN MEDIA WORLD: LANGUAGE AND STYLE SPECIFICS. *The Way of Science*, 52.
6. Khidoyatovna, S. S. (2022). NEW APPROACHES IN THE STUDY OF MEDIA TEXTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(3), 368-372.
7. Якубова, Ф. А. (2023). ГАЗЕТА МАТЕРИАЛЛАРИНИ ТАҲРИР ЖАРАЁНИДАГИ ЎЗИГА ХОСЛИКЛАР. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(10), 455-458